

MultiXscale

Report on stable, shared software stack

MultiXscale Deliverable 1.3
Deliverable Type: Report
Delivered in December, 2024

MultiXscale
EuroHPC Centre of Excellence for
Multiscale Modelling

Co-funded by
the European Union

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

Acknowledgement

Funded by the European Union. This work has received funding from the European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No 101093169.

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (JU). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Project and Deliverable Information

Project Title Project Ref. Project Website EuroHPC Project Officer	MultiXscale: EuroHPC Centre of Excellence for Multiscale Modelling Grant Agreement 101093169 https://www.multixscale.eu Dr. Matteo Mascagni
Deliverable ID Deliverable Nature Dissemination Level Contractual Date of Delivery Actual Date of Delivery	D1.3 Report Public Project Month 24 (31 st December, 2024) 30 th December, 2024
Description of Deliverable	Final report on the development of a stable, shared software stack

Document Control Information

Document	Title:	Report on stable, shared software stack
	ID:	D1.3
	Version:	As of December, 2024
	Status:	Accepted by SC
	Available at:	https://www.multixscale.eu/deliverables
	Document history:	Internal Project Management Link
Review	Review Status:	Reviewed
Authorship	Written by:	Alan O'Cais (University of Barcelona)
	Contributors:	Bob Dröge (RIJKSUNIGRON), Caspar van Leeuwen (SURF), Kenneth Hoste (UGent), Satish Kamath (SURF), Thomas Röblitz (UiB)
	Reviewed by:	Thomas Röblitz (UiB)
	Approved by:	Alan O'Cais (UB)

Document Keywords

Keywords:	MultiXscale, HPC, software, applications , infrastructure
-----------	---

30th December, 2024

Disclaimer: This deliverable has been prepared by the responsible Work Package of the Project in accordance with the Consortium Agreement and the Grant Agreement. It solely reflects the opinion of the parties to such agreements on a collective basis in the context of the Project and to the extent foreseen in such agreements.

Copyright notices: This deliverable was co-ordinated by Alan O'Cais¹ (University of Barcelona) on behalf of the MultiXscale consortium with contributions from Bob Dröge (RIJKSUNIGRON), Caspar van Leeuwen (SURF), Kenneth Hoste (UGent), Satish Kamath (SURF), Thomas Röblitz (UiB) . This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. To view a copy of this license, visit:

<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>

¹a.ocais@ub.edu

Contents

Executive Summary	1
1 Introduction	2
1.1 Scope of the deliverable	2
1.2 Target audience	2
1.3 Deliverable outline	2
1.4 Partner contributions	2
2 Design	3
2.1 Directory structure	3
2.1.1 Architecture-independent initialization	3
2.1.2 Initialization for different shells	3
2.1.3 EasyBuild configuration	3
2.1.4 Accelerators	4
2.1.5 Storing easystack files in folders dedicated to specific goals	4
2.2 Build recipes	5
2.2.1 Hooks	5
2.2.2 Example Pull Requests	5
2.3 Site customisation	6
2.3.1 Customising the user interface	6
2.3.2 Hardware drivers	6
2.3.3 Non-redistributable packages	6
2.3.4 Vendor interconnect libraries	7
2.3.5 Extending EESSI	7
2.4 Sync server for CernVM-FS network	7
3 Build and monitoring infrastructure	8
3.1 Build-test-and-deploy Bot	8
3.1.1 Building in the Cloud	8
3.1.2 Building on HPC systems	8
3.2 Deployment	9
3.3 Monitoring infrastructure	9
3.3.1 Status page	9
3.3.2 Monitoring dashboard	9
4 Hardware support	11
4.1 CPU	11
4.2 Accelerators	11
4.3 Interconnects	11
5 Available software	12
5.1 Testing and performance monitoring	12
5.2 Performance comparison against on-premise software stack	13
5.3 Growth over time	13
6 Adoption	16
6.1 EuroHPC Hosting Entities	16
6.2 Other entities	16
7 Conclusion and outlook	17
References	18

List of Figures

1	Directory structure for CPU-only and GPU-specific software and module files.	4
2	Status page for software.eessi.io	10
3	Dashboard that visualizes the statuses from the EESSI status page.	10
4	Two examples of Slack notifications sent by the Prometheus Alertmanager.	10
5	Dashboard showing the performance-over-time for one of the tests in the EESSI test suite	12

6	Point to point network bandwidth within a node and between 2 MPI processes, one on each node, executed on 3 different node architectures. Note: For the CPU architectures, module used is OSU-Micro-Benchmarks/7.1-1-gompi-2023a and for the GPU nodes, the module used is OSU-Micro-Benchmarks/7.2-gompi-2023a-CUDA-12.1.1.	13
7	Collective communication latencies starting from $\frac{1}{8}$ th of a node up to 16 nodes, executed on 3 different node architectures. Note: For the CPU architectures, module used is OSU-Micro-Benchmarks/7.1-1-gompi-2023a and for the GPU nodes, the module used is OSU-Micro-Benchmarks/7.2-gompi-2023a-CUDA-12.1.1.	13
8	Performance of three representative applications, executed on 2 different node architectures (Karolina-qcpu is zen2 which is the same CPU family as that of the Snellius-rome partition).	14
9	The growing number of software packages available in the EESSI production repository /cvmfs/software.eessi.io	15

List of Tables

1	Evolution of Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) over time. The columns "At proposal submission", "Estimated at project start" and "Projected at project end" are taken from the proposal for the MultiXscale project. The column "Observed at project start" shows that our estimates for the project start were too optimistic. However, the column "Achieved at mid-project", i.e., at the time of writing this deliverable, shows that we have made significant progress towards what we want to have achieved at the end of the project.	17
---	--	----

Executive Summary

This report describes the development and progress of the European Environment for Scientific Software Installations (EESSI) software stack under the EuroHPC MultiXscale project, and its progression to mature and stable state. The objective with this stack is to deliver a shared, optimized software stack that supports a range of architectures and scientific applications with a focus on performance and scalability for exascale systems. Over the past year, the project has made significant advancements, expanding its architectural support to now include nine CPU micro-architectures across x86_64 and aarch64 families, as well as enhancing GPU capabilities, particularly for NVIDIA's CUDA platforms. This has enabled support for a wide variety of configurations, including critical combinations (CPU micro-architecture & GPU accelerator) for EuroHPC systems like Deucalion and Karolina.

The software stack has grown substantially, increasing its available installations from 1,700 to over 9,000 in the last twelve months. The build infrastructure has been enhanced to utilize both commercial cloud platforms, such as AWS and Azure, and physical HPC systems, providing flexibility and access to diverse hardware. Rigorous performance benchmarking and automated testing across various HPC sites confirm that EESSI delivers performance comparable to locally installed software, with applications like ESPResSo and LAMMPS performing well across systems.

EESSI's infrastructure includes a comprehensive monitoring setup using Prometheus and Grafana, ensuring the stability and reliability of its distribution network. A new CernVM-FS sync server facilitates the creation of local mirrors, improving reliability during network outages and reducing load on public servers. Customization options allow institutions to tailor EESSI to specific needs, such as enabling GPU drivers or incorporating non-redistributable software like CUDA development tools. EasyBuild integration simplifies the addition of new software, enabling users to extend the stack as needed.

Adoption of EESSI has grown, with deployment across EuroHPC systems and numerous Tier-1 and Tier-2 HPC sites in Europe and beyond. EuroHPC systems like Vega, Karolina, and Deucalion have integrated the stack, and discussions are ongoing to include it in other major EuroHPC systems. The project envisions further expansions, including support for emerging architectures, additional GPU-enabled applications, and tools for artificial intelligence. Efforts to train researchers and refine developer workflows aim to broaden EESSI's adoption and usability, positioning it as a key resource in the EuroHPC ecosystem.

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope of the deliverable

This deliverable provides information about the results achieved in Task 1.1:

Providing a stable, optimized, shared scientific software stack with support for established system architectures.

Particularly, we focus on technical developments on top of the work reported in Deliverable D1.1 "Report on shared software stack prototype" [1]. Initially, the seven CPU micro-architectures `x86_64/generic`, `x86_64/intel/haswell`, `x86_64/intel/skylake_avx512`, `x86_64/amd/zen2`, `x86_64/amd/zen3`, `aarch64/generic`, `aarch64/neoverse_n1` and `aarch64/neoverse_v1` were supported. At the time of writing `x86_64/amd/zen4` and `aarch64/a64fx` are supported too (although not all software packages are available for them). The former was chosen because it is an architecture available at a partner of the MultiXscale consortium, the latter was chosen because it is used in a partition of the EuroHPC system Deucalion. Overall the number of *installations*, that is, any software package built for any CPU micro-architecture, has increased from about 1,700 to about 9,000 in the past 12 months.

EESSI, by design and by how software is built for it, is optimized for performance. It not only includes software built for a generic CPU micro-architecture of each of the supported CPU families - `x86_64` and `aarch64` - but also provides nearly full software stacks built for every of the nine supported CPU micro-architectures. The software is built and tested on CPUs providing the targeted micro-architecture, which ensures that the code paths optimized for the architecture are used and also tested during the build procedure. To further our confidence that EESSI provides performance-optimized software installations, we regularly run regression tests using the test suite developed in Task 1.3 and have also benchmarked key applications included in EESSI against *on-premise* installations. These show that software in EESSI delivers the same performance as locally installed software. Lastly, it is important to monitor the status of the EESSI software distribution network established via CernVM-FS servers and clients to make sure it is accessible without disruptions.

1.2 Target audience

This report is aimed at anyone who is interested in an overview of how EESSI's design, build and monitoring infrastructure, hardware support and available software has evolved over the past 12 months.

1.3 Deliverable outline

In Section 2 we provide an update about the design of EESSI including changes and additions to the directory structure of the CernVM-FS repository `/cvmfs/software.eessi.io`, describe build recipes for software packages, detail various means to customise EESSI at a site, and describe the additional mirror server added to EESSI's CernVM-FS network.

The build and monitoring infrastructure is described in Section 3. It includes new features for the *build-test-and-deploy bot*, provides an update on the deployment process and illustrates the monitoring infrastructure.

Section 4 provides an update on which CPU micro-architectures and GPUs are supported as well as how we ensure that different high-speed interconnects can be used with communication libraries such as OpenMPI.

In Section 5 we explain how we use the EESSI test suite (developed in Task 1.3) to monitor the performance of key applications across various EuroHPC systems as well as HPC clusters available to partners in the MultiXscale consortium. We also provide interesting insights comparing the installations provided by EESSI with those available from a local "on-premise" installation. Lastly, we show the steady increase of available software packages.

Section 6 provides an update on the adoption of EESSI (at which sites or systems it is made accessible) for EuroHPC hosting entities and other sites.

We conclude and provide an outlook in Section 7.

1.4 Partner contributions

All partners in Task 1.1 (UGent, SURE, RIJKSUNIGRON, UB and UiB) contributed as planned to the work described in this deliverable.

2 Design

This section highlights improvements of the design of EESSI compared to the prototype stack (see Deliverable D1.1 "Report on shared software stack prototype" [1]).

2.1 Directory structure

The core directory structure has been unchanged since the prototype stack that we reported about in Deliverable D1.1 "Report on shared software stack prototype" [1]. However, to add new functionality and to improve the support for accelerators, we adjusted the directory structure as follows:

- we added directories that store module files that can be used to initialize EESSI (see section 2.1.1),
- we created a directory `/cvmfs/software.eessi.io/versions/2023.06/init/lmod` which stores shell-specific scripts to initialize Lmod: A New Environment Module System (Lmod) and then use the module file for EESSI (see item above) to initialize EESSI (see section 2.1.2),
- we added a directory `/cvmfs/software.eessi.io/versions/2023.06/init/easybuild` which stores configuration files for adding software to EESSI with the EESSI-extend/2023.06-easybuild module (see section 2.1.3 for the configuration files and section 2.3.5 for the EESSI-extend module),
- under directories for installations for a specific CPU micro-architectures new subdirectories for accelerator software installations and module files were added (see section 2.1.4), *and*
- we started making use of additional sub directories for storing easystack files for distinct purposes (see section 2.1.5)

2.1.1 Architecture-independent initialization

To simplify the setup of the environment for EESSI, we created the module file

```
/cvmfs/software.eessi.io/versions/2023.06/init/modules/EESSI/2023.06.lua
```

Now, EESSI version 2023.06 can be initialized by running the two commands

```
module use /cvmfs/software.eessi.io/versions/2023.06/init/modules
module load EESSI/2023.06
```

In addition, we created a symbolic link from

```
/cvmfs/software.eessi.io/init/modules/EESSI/2023.06.lua
```

to

```
/cvmfs/software.eessi.io/versions/2023.06/init/modules/EESSI/2023.06.lua
```

which allows us to use a version-independent path for the command `module use` as shown in the two commands below.

```
module use /cvmfs/software.eessi.io/init/modules
module load EESSI/2023.06
```

This mechanism works for Lmod with version 8.6 or newer. For more detailed information, see [Loading an EESSI environment module](#) at the EESSI documentation web page.

2.1.2 Initialization for different shells

The prototype software stack supported the initialization of the EESSI environment for the bash shell by sourcing a bash script. Lmod, however, is shell-agnostic and its installation in the compatibility layer provides scripts to initialize Lmod for other shells such as `csh`, `fish`, `ksh` and `zsh`. Thus, we only need to provide minimal shell-specific initialization scripts which set up the environment for Lmod and then use a new module file to initialize EESSI. Using these scripts EESSI can be initialized by running the following command (for the bash shell)

```
source /cvmfs/software.eessi.io/versions/2023.06/init/lmod/bash
```

2.1.3 EasyBuild configuration

The new directory `/cvmfs/software.eessi.io/versions/2023.06/init/easybuild` contains a [configuration file for EasyBuild hooks](#) (see section 2.2.1) to be used with the EESSI-extend module (see section 2.3.5).

2.1.4 Accelerators

In the prototype stack, software packages with accelerator support such as NVIDIA GPUs were installed at the same directory level as CPU-only builds. This approach was based on the assumption that GPU-enabled software can be built *fat*, meaning that a single installation of a software package can support optimisations for a wide range of GPUs. However, this is not always the case, for example, Large-scale Atomic/Molecular Massively Parallel Simulator (LAMMPS) cannot be built *fat* and can only be optimised for a single CUDA compute capability per build. Thus, we have refined the directory structure by adding three levels as illustrated below

```
level_1 /      level_2          /   level_3
  accel / {nvidia,amd,intel} / {cc80,gfx90a}
```

on top of the software path (denoted by the environment variable \$EESSI_SOFTWARE_PATH). For example, software that is built for the Compute Unified Device Architecture (CUDA) compute capability 8.0 for zen2 CPUs is stored under the path

```
/cvmfs/software.eessi.io/versions/2023.06/software/linux/x86_64/amd/zen2/accel/nvidia/cc80
```

In that directory software packages are installed under the subdirectory `software` and module files are provided under the subdirectory `modules`. Fig. 1 illustrates the new directory structure.

Figure 1: Directory structure for CPU-only and GPU-specific software and module files.

2.1.5 Storing easystack files in folders dedicated to specific goals

We have begun to store easystack files in sub folders of the directory `easystacks/software.eessi.io/2023.06` in the branch `2023.06-software.eessi.io` of the [EESSI/software-layer repository on GitHub](#). Some of these directories exist only temporarily while others are expected to exist permanently.

Easystack files to build software for the CPU micro-architectures `zen4` and `a64fx` are stored under sub folders with these names. We expect that these folders only exist temporarily. They allow us to build up stacks for CPU micro-architectures that are not yet fully supported in EESSI. In particular, this allows us to tweak CI workflows that test for missing software builds for each of the supported CPU micro-architectures. Without special treatment, these workflows would fail until stacks for new CPU micro-architectures include all the software available for the other CPU micro-architectures.

In some cases, we need to rebuild a software package. To keep track of what packages were rebuilt, we did not simply add another command to the bot, say `bot: rebuild ...`, but rather kept information about what was rebuilt in separate easystack files in a different sub folder named `rebuilt`. The easystack files are named like `YYYYMMDD-eb-EBVERSION-short-label-describing-rebuild.yml`, where `YYYYMMDD` is the date when the pull request for the rebuild was created, `EBVERSION` is the EasyBuild version being used for rebuilding and the remainder is a very short description of the purpose of the rebuild or just the software package that will be rebuilt. At the time of writing, only 23 pull request to rebuild software packages were needed and ten of those were needed due to internal restructuring of the support for NVIDIA GPUs or improvements of the EESSI-extend modules. Rebuilding software packages occurs rarely.

Finally, to distinguish between software installations that only use CPUs and those that require a combination of CPUs and GPUs we created a new sub folder named `accel` which currently contains another sub folder named `nvidia`. That folder, i.e., `accel/nvidia`, contains easystack files for building GPU-enabled software. At the moment, the installation procedure does not make any use of the separation in the directory structure, so this is rather created to help maintainers of the EESSI stack to verify if a build requires GPUs or not.

2.2 Build recipes

Currently, EasyBuild is the only supported software package manager in EESSI. EasyBuild uses *easyconfigs* that contain key information about a software package to be built. Key information includes the name, version, sources, patches and dependencies. That information is then used by the EasyBuild framework employing *easyblocks* that define generic or tailored build procedures for software packages. In most cases, EESSI uses easyconfigs that are part of an EasyBuild release. In exceptional cases, for example, for newly added or updated easyconfigs or easyblocks may be used by providing special parameters (`-from-commit` or `-include-easyblocks-from-commit`) when running EasyBuild. In any case, our [contribution policy](#) requires that such updates to EasyBuild may only be used if their corresponding pull request has been merged.

2.2.1 Hooks

In some cases, the build procedure of a software package has to be tweaked for EESSI either because of its specific features (using `RPATH`, not using `LD_LIBRARY_PATH` and using OS-level libraries under a prefix path) or because it includes software installations for many different CPU and GPU architectures and using the same easyconfig to build a package across different architectures may not work without adjusting subtle details. EasyBuild provides the ability to run hooks at different stages of the build procedure. These hooks can be used for various purposes to let the build succeed in the specific EESSI environment. Typically, a hook is only used for a specific software package, specific software package version or for a specific CPU family or micro-architecture.

At the time of writing, building software for EESSI is using a total of 37 hooks across 9 types of hooks. The most used hook types are `parse_hook` (hooks for 11 software packages), `pre_configure_hook` (hooks for 10 software packages) and `pre_test_hook` (hooks for 6 software packages). Out of the 37 hooks, two are specifically made to resolve build issues on the `x86_64` CPU family, while 17 are made for the `aarch64` CPU family (most of them for the `neoverse_v1` and `a64fx` micro-architectures). This difference (needed number of hooks) between the two CPU families is likely a result of `x86_64` CPUs being much more accessible to developers and thus being better tested than `aarch64` CPUs.

2.2.2 Example Pull Requests

In EESSI, all software is added via pull requests to the [EESSI/software-layer repository on GitHub](#). Here, we briefly illustrate the three main elements used in these pull requests.

(1) Adding a software for which the EasyBuild release contains an easyconfig

[Pull request 782 to the EESSI/software-layer GitHub repository](#) illustrates the addition of two software packages. It uses the EasyBuild release 4.9.4 which already contains the needed easyconfigs. The pull request only changes the `easystack` file

```
easystacks/software.eessi.io/2023.06/a64fx/eessi-2023.06-eb-4.9.4-2023b.yml
```

by adding the following two lines

```
- ESPResSo-4.2.2-foss-2023b.eb
- pyMBE-0.8.0-foss-2023b.eb
```

(2) Adding a software for which the EasyBuild release does not contain an easyconfig yet

[Pull request 748 to the EESSI/software-layer GitHub repository](#) illustrates the addition of a software package for which the EasyBuild release 4.9.3 does not contain the needed easyconfigs yet. The pull request only changes the `easystack` file

```
easystacks/software.eessi.io/2023.06/accel/nvidia/eessi-2023.06-eb-4.9.3-2023a-CUDA.yml
```

by adding the four lines

```
- ESPResSo-4.2.2-foss-2023a-CUDA-12.1.1.eb:
  options:
    # see https://github.com/easybuilders/easybuild-easyconfigs/pull/21440
    from-commit: 5525968921d7b5eae54f7d16391201e17ffae13c
```

The easyconfig to be used is `ESPResSo-4.2.2-foss-2023a-CUDA-12.1.1.eb`. Because that easyconfig does not exist yet in the EasyBuild release 4.9.3, we add additional options (keyword `options`). With the keyword `from-commit` and the value `5525968921d7b5eae54f7d16391201e17ffae13c` we specify that EasyBuild shall use this commit to the [easybuilders/easybuild-easyconfigs GitHub repository](#) when building `ESPResSo`.

(3) Adding a software that requires a hook to let its building succeed

[Pull request 797 to the EESSI/software-layer GitHub repository](#) illustrates a little more complex case that requires new or updated easyconfigs *and* further customisations of the build procedure with *hooks*. With hooks EasyBuild allows to customise the build procedure to the specific needs of an environment such as EESSI. Hooks can be defined to run before or after many of the build steps (a complete list of user-definable hooks can be obtained by running the command `eb -list-hooks`).

Pull request 797 uses a `pre_configure` hook, i.e., the code is executed **before** the configure step of the build procedure is run. In this example, the hook ensures that certain parts (libraries and include files) of the `binutils` package are found. In EESSI that package is included in the compatibility layer and it is also a filtered dependency which means EasyBuild will not install a copy of this package into the software layer, but rather relies on the installation in the compatibility layer.

2.3 Site customisation

Installing EESSI is enough to get started with the EESSI software stack on a CPU-based system. However, additional site-specific customisation is necessary in other cases, such as

- site-specific configuration / tuning of the MPI libraries provided by EESSI
- enabling GPU support on GPU-based systems
- overriding EESSI's MPI library with an ABI compatible host MPI
- making additional software available

To allow such site-specific configuration, the EESSI repository includes a special directory where system administrators can install files that can be picked up by the software installations included in EESSI. This special directory is located in `/cvmfs/software.eessi.io/host_injections`, and it is a CernVM-FS Variant Symlink: a symbolic link for which the target can be controlled by the CernVM-FS client configuration (for more info, see '[Variant Symlinks](#)' in the official CernVM-FS documentation). Having a fixed location on the filesystem which is writable by the host site allows for a number of customisation possibilities, some of which we describe in the next sections.

2.3.1 Customising the user interface

The EESSI user interface is `Lmod`, we can allow for local additional [configuration of Lmod via hooks](#). This can be used to, for example, set additional environment variables that can tune an MPI implementation for the system, or to curate the software applications that are exposed to end users.

2.3.2 Hardware drivers

A runtime dynamic linker (`ld-linux*.so`) is a system component responsible for loading and linking shared libraries (or dynamic libraries) to a program during its execution. Via the *compatibility* layer, EESSI provides its own runtime dynamic linker. Since EESSI controls the dynamic linker it can control the default locations where it looks for *trusted* libraries. By appending trusted locations under `/cvmfs/software.eessi.io/host_injections`, we give the site the capability to inject driver libraries into EESSI.

This approach is currently leveraged to allow for the injection of the host NVIDIA GPU drivers for use by EESSI, and is what allows us to ship functional, multi-platform CUDA-enabled applications. EESSI also ships helper scripts that can discover, inject and verify the necessary GPU driver libraries.

2.3.3 Non-redistributable packages

Legal restrictions may only allow EESSI to ship the runtime environment, not the development environment, for some packages. CUDA and the Intel compilers are examples of such cases. Via the use of `host_injections`, we can replace all content that is not part of the runtime with symlinks to a specific location under `host_injections`. We then add scripting to EESSI which can fix the broken symlinks locally on the host system, making the development environment fully available for the application.

We currently use this approach to allow CUDA to load as a module under EESSI. We have hooks for `Lmod` in place such that the module can only be loaded if the necessary symlinks have been unbroken (otherwise helper text is printed to explain how to do this).

2.3.4 Vendor interconnect libraries

All of the MPI-enabled software available in EESSI is configured to prefer the required MPI libraries from a location under `host_injections`, and to use the MPI libraries shipped with EESSI as a fallback. This approach means that a site can inject their own version of the MPI libraries that may have been tuned for a specific interconnect.

This approach relies on the ABI-compatibility guarantees of the MPI implementations. It has been shown to work with the [AWS Elastic Fabric Adaptor](#) where small but measurable improvements in MPI performance were observed when using the vendor-supplied MPI libraries.

2.3.5 Extending EESSI

While the EESSI environment contains a large amount of software, there will always be software that is *not* available through EESSI, for example because it does not satisfy the requirements in the [contribution policy](#). For that reason, a module `EESSI-extend/2023.06-easybuild` was created which easily allows users to [build additional software on top of EESSI using EasyBuild](#). The module supports three main use cases:

1. An HPC site making EESSI available that wants to build on top of EESSI and make those module available to all their users.
2. A group of users that want to build on top of EESSI in a shared directory, to which all group members have access.
3. An individual user that wants to build on top of EESSI in a personal (home) directory.

The `EESSI-extend` module makes sure that EasyBuild is configured in the same way as it is for the installations in EESSI itself.

Alternatively, users might want to build on top of EESSI manually (i.e. without using EasyBuild). Technically, [building on top of EESSI manually is already possible and documented](#), but it requires a user to have relatively intricate knowledge on concepts like `RPATH` and setting the interpreter for their executable. Depending of the needs of our end-users, we may come up with additional solutions to facilitate this approach as part of task 1.5.

2.4 Sync server for CernVM-FS network

One major addition has been done the CernVM-FS infrastructure that we use to host the EESSI software stack: a sync server has been introduced that can be used by anyone to set up a private Stratum 1 mirror server. By doing so, sites will have a full mirror of the EESSI stack nearby, and they can, for instance, make their HPC cluster resilient against external network outages. Without a private Stratum 1 server, such an outage would make the software stack mostly unavailable, with the exception of files that are still in local caches. For this reason, and also to reduce the load on the public EESSI Stratum 1 servers, we strongly recommend this approach in the EESSI documentation for administrators that want to make EESSI available on infrastructures consisting of a larger number of clients (like HPC clusters). In order to facilitate the process of setting up a private Stratum 1 server, an Ansible playbook is available and [additional documentation](#) has been written. In practice, this has already been used and tested by several sites that are now hosting their own Stratum 1 server.

The sync server has been set up in AWS using S3 storage as backend. A cronjob running on the sync servers ensures that the entire contents of the EESSI stack is synchronized from the EESSI Stratum 0 server to S3 storage every 10 minutes. Private Stratum 1 servers can synchronize directly with this S3 storage without going through the sync server itself. This takes advantage of all the features that AWS S3 offers in terms of availability, scalability, and performance.

Other than this, no significant changes have been made to the CernVM-FS infrastructure itself, and it has been running without any issues for the last year; no issues have been reported by users, nor by our new monitoring setup. The latter will be further discussed in section 3.3.

3 Build and monitoring infrastructure

The build infrastructure initially consisted of a single cluster on AWS. It has been expanded during the last twelve months in the following ways:

- we added a new build cluster on the Azure cloud platform to build for the zen4 microarchitecture;
- we added another new build cluster on the Azure cloud platform to support building for the new developers CernVM-FS repository `/cvmfs/dev.eessi.io`;
- we installed the *build-test-and-deploy bot* on the Arriesgado RISC-V cluster and on the EuroHPC system Deucalion which provides access to `arch64/a64fx` CPU micro-architecture; *and*,
- preparations have been made to use physical HPC clusters (both EuroHPC clusters and local/national clusters available to MultiXscale project partners) for building GPU-enabled software.

3.1 Build-test-and-deploy Bot

The *build-test-and-deploy bot* is a Python application that reacts to events generated on code management platforms such as GitHub. It is used to build all the software that is provided by the production repository `/cvmfs/software.eessi.io` and is an efficient tool to manage community contributions - additions of software installations via pull requests to the [EESSI/software-layer GitHub repository](#). The initial efforts to implement the bot are described in Deliverable D5.1 "Community contribution policy and GitHub App" [2].

Since then, four releases for the bot have been made available. Overall, the major changes were:

- the new bot command `status` provides an overview of the build status of different jobs in a single pull request; with a growing number of build clusters this command will become more and more useful to keep track of various builds across multiple clusters;
- increased flexibility when uploading tarballs to an S3 bucket so that tarballs for the same pull request can be put in a single directory which enables more efficient processing of them for a growing number and more diverse supported architectures;
- making the bot fully agnostic to what it builds, so that it can be more easily be used for other scenarios, such as building for `/cvmfs/dev.eessi.io`, or building and installing software locally, i.e., on a network file system;
- adding support to the bot `build` command to build for specific accelerators;
- automatic clean-up of used disk space when a pull request has been closed or merged;
- enabling custom job submission options defined by the (GitHub) repository the bot builds for.

The full list of changes is provided in the [release notes on GitHub](#).

3.1.1 Building in the Cloud

From early on, the EESSI community has created and maintained build infrastructure on commercial Cloud platforms - namely, on AWS and Azure. This was made possible by receiving sponsored Cloud credits from both AWS and Azure. Building in the Cloud provides several advantages for our cross-border / cross-organization collaboration:

- access to the resources is flexible, which allows us to provide access to maintainers of the software stack regardless of their institutional affiliation;
- infrastructure as code tools (such as [Magic Castle](#)) allow us to quickly spin-up, adjust and tear-down resources,
- a large variety of hardware types is available, thus allowing us to build for many architectures using a single system

Apart from the Azure and AWS build clusters that build for the production repository `/cvmfs/software.eessi.io`, we have provisioned a separate build cluster for allowing selected developers to build and deploy through our development repository `/cvmfs/dev.eessi.io`. This separation in two clusters is done for security reasons.

3.1.2 Building on HPC systems

While building in the Cloud provides several benefits for EESSI maintainers (unbureaucratic access, large variety of CPU micro-architectures accessible), building GPU-enabled software on Cloud VMs that are configured with GPUs can be quite costly as well as suffering from low availability. As a result, we have begun to also build on physical

HPC clusters that are available at partner sites or part of the EuroHPC ecosystem. They complement our build infrastructure on Cloud platforms by adding CPU+GPU combinations that are difficult to find or costly to use on Cloud platforms, they help in diversifying the range of resources we can utilise to build a growing shared software stack, and they also provide access to CPU micro-architectures such as `aarch64/a64fx` that are not available on Cloud platforms.

While using personal accounts on HPC systems to build software for EESSI is easily possible for a single maintainer or developer, it creates a number of issues. Keeping the build infrastructure's configuration synchronised across several bot instances may become cumbersome and error-prone. In addition, the deployment part where tarballs are uploaded to an S3 bucket may become ineffective because several maintainers would have to trigger deployments for their "private" bot instances. Moreover, the credentials to write to the S3 bucket would have to be shared with all maintainers. To avoid these complications, we are pursuing so-called *service accounts* which would run a single instance of the bot on an HPC cluster and provide access to several maintainers of the software stack. Finally, having used the *build-test-and-deploy bot* for well over a year on Cloud platforms and others who use it to build their local software stacks with it, also reassured us that the bot can be deployed on physical HPC clusters.

3.2 Deployment

The deployment process has mostly remained unchanged in the last year, as the setup that we used for the pilot repository turned out to work very well. This is a semi-automated process, with two places where EESSI maintainers need to take action. First, after a successful build performed by the bot, an EESSI maintainer with deploy permissions has to set a "bot: deploy" label on the pull request to make the bot upload the build artifacts (tarballs containing the installations) to an object storage. Just before these tarballs will actually be ingested to the software repository, additional "staging" pull requests will be opened for these uploaded tarballs, and an EESSI maintainer with ingest permissions will have to approve these.

There have been only minor changes that have been made to streamline the review process. For instance, the staging pull requests now show a clearer overview of the contents of the tarballs, the repository to which they will be ingested, and a link to the original pull request from which these builds originated.

As mentioned in section 3.1, some additional changes have been made to handle the growing number of tarballs. Though the process has proven to work really well, we plan to make some additional changes in this aspect to make the reviewing process even smoother for the increasing number of builds. For instance, more automated checks could be done here to analyze the builds of the same software for different CPU targets, and the result of these checks could be made available.

3.3 Monitoring infrastructure

An important new component that was built and further developed last year is the monitoring setup that monitors the CernVM-FS setup used to make the EESSI software stack available.

3.3.1 Status page

A pilot version of an EESSI status page was redeveloped in Rust for the new production repository, and this is available at <https://status.eessi.io/>. This status page gives a quick overview of the current status of the individual servers and repositories, for instance whether or not servers are up and whether or not they are in sync with the Stratum 0. As the outage of an individual server should not immediately affect end users, it also shows a more global status of the infrastructure as a whole.

The status page generator is running on an AWS virtual machine, and it is scraping information from all CernVM-FS servers every 10 minutes. This information is then used to evaluate a set of rules for all the different statuses, and finally it generate an up-to-date version of the status page, as seen in Fig. 2.

3.3.2 Monitoring dashboard

Besides have a user-facing status page, we also set up an admin-focused monitoring stack and dashboard based on [Prometheus](#) and [Grafana](#).

[Prometheus node exporters](#) have been installed on all the EESSI CernVM-FS servers in order to collect metrics about these servers (these include metrics about CPU, memory, disks, network, and more), and the central Prometheus server scrapes these metrics every 30 seconds. The metrics are visualized using a Grafana dashboard, allowing the EESSI maintainers to have a quick glance at the current and historical status of all individual servers.

Besides this, the Prometheus server also scrapes all the information collected by the EESSI status page, which makes it possible to visualize the statuses over time. An examples of this is shown in Fig. 3, where Fig. 3a shows a visualization

Figure 2: Status page for software.eessi.io

of these statuses over a 30-day period, while we zoomed in on a particular issue in Fig. 3b. Note that the issue in this visualization was not really a failure, but instead it was caused by a large software ingest that took an extended period to synchronize to the Stratum 1 servers.

(a) Last 30 days.

(b) Zooming in on a particular issue.

Figure 3: Dashboard that visualizes the statuses from the EESSI status page.

Finally, in order to be alerted right away in case of issues, we also set up a [Prometheus Alertmanager instance](#) with a set of Prometheus alert rules. These rules define if and when alerts should be fired, and these are currently sent to a Slack channel to which only EESSI CernVM-FS administrator have access. Two examples of such alerts can be seen in Fig. 4: in Fig. 4a Prometheus found that the Stratum 0 servers was unreachable for a really short while, and this was resolved a few minutes later when it could be scraped again. In Fig. 4b, the EESSI status went to critical for a short while, again because a large ingest took longer than expected to make its way to the Stratum 1 servers.

(a) Short network hiccup of the Stratum 0 server.

(b) EESSI overall status is critical.

Figure 4: Two examples of Slack notifications sent by the Prometheus Alertmanager.

4 Hardware support

At the time of writing, EESSI's production CernVM-FS repository (`/cvmfs/software.eessi.io`) supports nine CPU micro-architectures, NVIDIA GPU accelerators as well as InfiniBand and OmniPath high-speed interconnect networks.

4.1 CPU

The following nine CPU micro-architectures for the two CPU families `x86_64` and `aarch64` are currently fully² supported in EESSI:

CPU family	Supported CPU micro-architectures
<code>x86_64</code>	<code>generic, haswell, skylake_avx512, zen2, zen3, zen4</code>
<code>aarch64</code>	<code>generic, neoverse_n1, neoverse_v1</code>

Additionally, there is a growing number of software installations available for the CPU micro-architecture `aarch64/a64fx` which is the CPU on the EuroHPC system Deucalion. In particular, the key applications in MultiXscale - ESPResSo, LAMMPS and waLBerla - are already available for that architecture and can be used on the system.

In the future, we may extend the support to other CPU micro-architectures such as Intel Sapphire Rapids, NVIDIA Grace and/or AMD Zen5 based what is available in EuroHPC JU systems, the needs of the scientific community and interest in the wider EESSI community. All that is needed is access to machines we can build the software on. The build infrastructure has proven to be flexible and scalable to accommodate new CPU micro-architectures and accelerators such as NVIDIA GPUs.

4.2 Accelerators

In Deliverable D1.1 "Report on shared software stack prototype" [1], we reported about support for NVIDIA GPU accelerators already. While the basic principles of supporting NVIDIA GPUs remain unchanged - runtime libraries for CUDA and other necessary toolkits are included in EESSI adhering to their redistribution licenses *and* EESSI provides scripts to make drivers accessible in a standardized location - we have refined the directory structure for GPU-enabled installations (cf. section 2.1.4).

Today, EESSI supports GPU-enabled installations for both ESPResSo and LAMMPS (two key applications in MultiXscale) as well as for GROMACS (a very popular molecular dynamics simulation package which is a key application in the EuroHPC JU Centre of Excellence BioExcel). At the time of writing installations for the CPU+GPU combinations `zen2+cc80` and `zen3+cc80` are available through the EESSI production software repository `/cvmfs/software.eessi.io`. The term `cc80` corresponds to the CUDA compute capability 8.0 which is supported on NVIDIA A100 GPUs. The combinations were chosen because these are found in the EuroHPC systems Deucalion (`zen2+cc80`), Karolina (`zen3+cc80`), Meluxina (`zen2+cc80`) and Vega (`zen2+cc80`).

However, with the refined directory structure for supporting accelerators (cf. section 2.1.4) the project is well-prepared to build software for additional combinations of CPU+GPU in the future.

4.3 Interconnects

By design, the EESSI MPI libraries are built "fat", which means attempting to include support for as many interconnect fabrics as possible. This is done by leveraging both [UCX](#) and [libfabric](#) in our build of OpenMPI. As a result, EESSI supports both NVIDIA InfiniBand and Intel OmniPath high-speed interconnect networks "out of the box". These may however benefit from additional tuning using environment variables (see section 2.3.1).

In addition, EESSI supports overriding the included MPI libraries with a site-specific alternative such as a vendor-provided MPI (see section 2.3.4).

²Software packages built with the toolchain `foss/2022b` (GCC compiler version 12.2) are not supported on `zen4`, because `zen4` requires GCC compiler version 12.3 or newer.

5 Available software

The variety of software packages available in EESSI is steadily increasing. It thus becomes more attractive for users because they may likely find a package they need or they may benefit from all the libraries and tools their application needs to build or to run. In addition to the growing number of software packages available through EESSI, we also benefit from more and more portable regression tests that are being developed in Task 1.3. These tests are regularly run on a variety of systems to obtain valuable performance data over time.

5.1 Testing and performance monitoring

Testing is essential to ensure the quality and stability (including performance stability) of the shared software stack. A detailed strategy is outlined in Deliverable D1.2 "Plan for the design of a portable test suite" [3]. We will summarize it here.

Testing is done at different stages:

- upon deployment of new software, as part of a CI workflow, and
- on a regular (e.g. daily or weekly) basis.

When contributing new software, if that software comes with a unit test suite it is run at the end of a build by EasyBuild. Furthermore, a selection of tests from the EESSI test suite is run after the build. If there is an application-specific test in the test suite, this is run. Otherwise, a set of default tests is run.

As of December 2024, the EESSI test suite is also run on a regular (daily or weekly) basis on several systems, including the EuroHPC systems Vega and Karolina, as well as several systems managed by MultiXscale project partners (Snellius, 3 Norwegian systems, HPC-UGent Clusters).

Test results are displayed through a dashboard (Figure 5). Such a dashboard allows us to spot performance regressions, and trace it back to a date on which they were introduced. Being able to narrow down the moment of introduction to a single day is helpful in identifying the cause of the regression. Note that a performance measurement is the result of interplay of the entire infrastructure, from hardware, to system, to software. Thus, a performance regression could be related to either of the three. By regularly testing on multiple systems, we can easily isolate issues that are specific to the software: they would show regressions on all systems, introduced simultaneously.

Figure 5: Dashboard showing the performance-over-time for one of the tests in the EESSI test suite

5.2 Performance comparison against on-premise software stack

To verify that the deployment of software through EESSI does not negatively affect performance, the performance of selected applications in EESSI and in a local software environment was compared. This comparison was done on Snellius, the HPC system hosted by SURE, so that we could easily install additional modules in the local module environment to match the versions from EESSI.

The comparison was done using tests from the EESSI test suite. Applications selected were OSU-Micro-Benchmarks (as a low-level benchmark, see Figures 6 and 7) and LAMMPS and ESPResSo (as high level applications from MultiXscale, see Figure 8). Apart from the point-to-point benchmarks, each application is executed from $\frac{1}{8}$ th of a node up to 16 nodes. The OSU tests were also performed on GPUs.

Figure 6: Point to point network bandwidth within a node and between 2 MPI processes, one on each node, executed on 3 different node architectures. Note: For the CPU architectures, module used is OSU-Micro-Benchmarks/7.1-1-gompi-2023a and for the GPU nodes, the module used is OSU-Micro-Benchmarks/7.2-gompi-2023a-CUDA-12.1.1.

Figure 7: Collective communication latencies starting from $\frac{1}{8}$ th of a node up to 16 nodes, executed on 3 different node architectures. Note: For the CPU architectures, module used is OSU-Micro-Benchmarks/7.1-1-gompi-2023a and for the GPU nodes, the module used is OSU-Micro-Benchmarks/7.2-gompi-2023a-CUDA-12.1.1.

Overall, no systematic significant differences were found between the performance of the EESSI software stack vs. the internal software stack. There are some points where the performance of the EESSI module is slightly better, such as in the case of ESPResSo (Figure 8) and slightly worse, such as in the case of the OSU allreduce benchmark (Figure 7). It is important to mention that these differences are not significant and are subject to other parameters such as system load, type of nodes assigned to a particular job, etc. The GROMACS test is not executed beyond 512 cores, since further decomposition of the domain in the test was not possible. GROMACS 2024.1 is present with slightly different toolchains internally on Snellius and on EESSI, the toolchain on Snellius being 2023a and on EESSI being 2023b.

5.3 Growth over time

We are continuously adding more software to the EESSI software stacks as easyconfigs for them become available or as they are requested by the EuroHPC community or external contributors. Prominent examples for software used by other EuroHPC JU Centres of Excellence are Extrae, Paraver and Score-P which are performance analysis tools used by the [PoP CoE](#). Figure 9 shows the steadily growing number of software installations - in the 12 months since

Figure 8: Performance of three representative applications, executed on 2 different node architectures (Karolina-qcpu is zen2 which is the same CPU family as that of the Snellius-rome partition).

we reported about the prototype software stack (see D1.1 [1]) we added about 800 software packages to the software repository, most of them are built for nine CPU micro-architectures.

Figure 9: The growing number of software packages available in the EESSI production repository `/cvmfs/software.eessi.io`

6 Adoption

In this section, we provide a brief overview of systems or sites where EESSI is available. To provide a full overview, we list the access that was already reported in Deliverable D1.1 "Report on shared software stack prototype" [1] and the new systems that have been added since then.

6.1 EuroHPC Hosting Entities

EESSI is becoming increasingly available across HPC sites. In order to provide a continuously updated overview of systems that provide access to the software stack, a dedicated [page](#) has been created on the EESSI documentation portal. We regularly update this page whenever we obtain new information, and we also invite contributors to provide updates if they are aware of missing entries.

As reported in Deliverable D1.1 [1], the EuroHPC sites [Vega](#) in Slovenia and [Karolina](#) in Czechia provide native access to EESSI. Recently, EESSI access has also been enabled on the EuroHPC system [Deucalion](#) in Portugal for the partition that contains a64fx CPUs. Furthermore, we are in dialogue with other EuroHPC hosting entities in order to make EESSI available on their systems. At MareNostrum 5, Meluxina and JUPITER; EESSI is actively being explored as a solution to provide a large uniform software stack.

6.2 Other entities

In addition to the EuroHPC Hosting Entities, EESSI is available in a number of Tier-1 and Tier-2 sites. We note that this is not necessarily an exhaustive list, as our availability data come from volunteer contributions to [our documentation](#) and first-hand knowledge of sites the project's members are affiliated to or otherwise have contact with.

To our knowledge and at the time of writing, EESSI is available in the following HPC sites:

- Belgium
 - Ghent University: Tier-2 clusters and VSC Tier-1 cluster Hortense
 - Vrije Universiteit Brussel: Hydra
- Germany
 - EMBL Heidelberg: HPC cluster
 - University of Stuttgart: Ant HPC cluster
- Greece
 - Aristotle University of Thessaloniki: Aristotle HPC cluster
- Netherlands
 - SURF: Spider HTC cluster, Research Cloud and Tier-1 cluster Snellius
 - University of Groningen: Hábrók HPC cluster and managed Linux workspace (LWP)
- Norway
 - Sigma2 AS / Norwegian Research Infrastructure Services: Betzy, Fram, and Saga HPC clusters.
 - Norwegian Ai Cloud: VMs can be launched on Google and Azure Clouds as well as on the local OpenStack-based platform [NREC](#)
- Spain
 - Barcelona Supercomputing Center: thunder, arriesgado-fedora37 and arriesgado-hirsute (the arriesgado systems provide RISC-V CPUs and use `/cvmfs/riscv.eessi.io`)
- United States of America
 - Michigan State University, Institute for Cyber-Enabled Research (ICER)
- Commercial cloud providers
 - AWS Parallel Cluster
- Cloud provisioning tools
 - [Magic Castle](#)

7 Conclusion and outlook

The EESSI stack has grown into a large uniform software stack that can be accessed on any Linux machine anywhere in the world. Not only is it designed to provide optimal performance, we have also developed tools to monitor that it actually does provide performance on par with software installed locally on a system. The evolution of Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) shown in Table 1 clearly shows the significant progress we have achieved during the course of the project so far. The various improvements and adjustments discussed in this deliverable illustrate that we continuously develop EESSI further to address the needs of the scientific community, the EuroHPC community of users, other Centres of Excellence and Hosting Entities. Thus, we hope EESSI becomes a valuable and useful service for many researchers in their daily work.

In the future we will work on improving the readiness of features as projected in Table 1 and engage with users and sites to provide software and tools they need to make best use of EESSI. We also want to expand the available software, support new CPU micro-architectures, extend list of the GPU-enabled software (particularly, to support frameworks needed for AI), and train researchers and developers in using EESSI.

Feature	At proposal submission, 4/2022	Estimated at project start, 1/2023	Observed at project start, 1/2023	Achieved at mid-project, 12/2024	Projected at project end, 12/2026
EESSI limited common stack	TRL 8	TRL 9	TRL 8	TRL 9	TRL 9
EESSI full common stack	TRL 6	TRL 8	TRL 6	TRL 8	TRL 9
Semi-automatic build of software	TRL 6	TRL 8	TRL 7	TRL 9	TRL 9
Building software on top of EESSI	TRL 6	TRL 9	TRL 6	TRL 8	TRL 9
Regression Testing	TRL 6	TRL 7	TRL 6	TRL 9	TRL 9
Distribution infrastructure	TRL 8	TRL 9	TRL 8	TRL 9	TRL 9
Monitoring infrastructure	TRL 4	TRL 6	TRL 5	TRL 7	TRL 9
GPU support	TRL 6	TRL 7	TRL 6	TRL 9	TRL 9
Integration with 3rd party services	TRL 7	TRL 8	TRL 7	TRL 9	TRL 9
Community-specific stacks	TRL 4	TRL 5	TRL 4	TRL 7	TRL 8/9
Enhanced developer workflows	TRL 5	TRL 6	TRL 5	TRL 7	TRL 8/9

Table 1: Evolution of Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) over time. The columns "At proposal submission", "Estimated at project start" and "Projected at project end" are taken from the proposal for the MultiXscale project. The column "Observed at project start" shows that our estimates for the project start were too optimistic. However, the column "Achieved at mid-project", i.e., at the time of writing this deliverable, shows that we have made significant progress towards what we want to have achieved at the end of the project.

References

Acronyms used

EESSI European Environment for Scientific Software Installations

HPC High Performance Computing

Software mentioned

CUDA Compute Unified Device Architecture

LAMMPS Large-scale Atomic/Molecular Massively Parallel Simulator

Lmod Lmod: A New Environment Module System

URLs referenced

Page ii

<https://www.multixscale.eu> ... <https://www.multixscale.eu>

<https://www.multixscale.eu/deliverables> ... <https://www.multixscale.eu/deliverables>

Internal Project Management Link ... <https://github.com/multixscale/planning/issues/103>

a.ocais@ub.edu ... <mailto:a.ocais@ub.edu>

<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0> ... <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>

Page 3

Loading an EESSI environment module ... https://www.eessi.io/docs/using_eessi/setting_up_environment/#loading-an-eessi-environment-module

configuration file for EasyBuild hooks ... <https://docs.easybuild.io/hooks/>

Page 4

EESSI/software-layer repository on GitHub ... <https://github.com/EESSI/software-layer>

Page 5

contribution policy ... https://www.eessi.io/docs/adding_software/contribution_policy/

EESSI/software-layer repository on GitHub ... <https://github.com/EESSI/software-layer>

Pull request 782 to the EESSI/software-layer GitHub repository ... <https://github.com/EESSI/software-layer/pull/782>

Pull request 748 to the EESSI/software-layer GitHub repository ... <https://github.com/EESSI/software-layer/pull/748>

easybuilders/easybuild-easyconfigs GitHub repository ... <https://github.com/easybuilders/easybuild-easyconfigs>

Pull request 797 to the EESSI/software-layer GitHub repository ... <https://github.com/EESSI/software-layer/pull/797>

Page 6

Installing EESSI ... https://www.eessi.io/docs/getting_access/native_installation/

'Variant Symlinks' in the official CernVM-FS documentation ... <https://cvmfs.readthedocs.io/en/stable/cpt-repo.html#variant-symlinks>

configuration of Lmod via hooks ... https://lmod.readthedocs.io/en/latest/170_hooks.html

Page 7

AWS Elastic Fabric Adaptor ... <https://aws.amazon.com/hpc/efa/>

contribution policy ... https://www.eessi.io/docs/adding_software/contribution_policy/

build additional software on top of EESSI using EasyBuild ... https://www.eessi.io/docs/using_eessi/building_on_eessi/#building-software-on-top-of-eessi-with-easybuild

building on top of EESSI manually is already possible and documented ... https://www.eessi.io/docs/using_eessi/building_on_eessi/#manually-building-software-op-top-of-eessi-without-easybuild

additional documentation ... https://www.eessi.io/docs/filesystem_layer/stratum1/

Page 8

EESSI/software-layer GitHub repository ... <https://github.com/EESSI/software-layer>

release notes on GitHub ... <https://github.com/EESSI/eessi-bot-software-layer/releases>

Magic Castle ... https://github.com/ComputeCanada/magic_castle/tree/main/docs

Page 9

<https://status.eessi.io/> ... <https://status.eessi.io/>

Prometheus ... <https://prometheus.io/>

Grafana ... <https://grafana.com/oss/grafana/>

Prometheus node exporters ... <https://grafana.com/oss/prometheus/exporters/node-exporter/>

Page 10

Prometheus Alertmanager instance ... <https://prometheus.io/docs/alerting/latest/alertmanager/>

Page 11

UCX... <https://github.com/openucx/ucx>

libfabric ... <https://ofiwg.github.io/libfabric/>

Page 13

PoP CoE ... <https://www.pop-coe.eu>

Page 16

page ... <https://www.eessi.io/docs/systems/>

Vega ... <https://doc.vega.izum.si/eessi/>

Karolina ... <https://docs.it4i.cz/software/eessi/>

Deucalion ... <https://www.macc.fcn.pt/resources#deucalion>

our documentation ... <https://www.eessi.io/docs/systems/#other-european-systems>

NREC ... <https://nrec.no>

Magic Castle ... https://github.com/ComputeCanada/magic_castle/blob/main/README.md

Citations

- [1] P. Santos Neves and B. Dröge, "D1.1 - report on shared software stack prototype," Jan. 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10451701>
- [2] T. Röblitz and K. Hoste, "D5.1 - community contribution policy and github app," Jan. 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10451793>
- [3] C. van Leeuwen, K. Hoste, and L. Peeters, "D1.2 - plan for the design of a portable test suite," Jan. 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10451718>